

1 **CDCA2 is differentially expressed in glioblastoma.**

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6 Glioblastoma is difficult to treat and patients are often provided poor prognosis (1), indicating a
7 requirement for therapeutic target identification and drug development. Differentially expressed genes
8 represent by definition among the most promising targets for the development of novel chemotherapies (2,
9 3). We predict therapeutic index is intrinsically linked to differential expression which can be
10 comprehensively and blindly determined using whole transcriptome data, further limiting toxicity by
11 design (4). We mined published and public microarray and RNA-sequencing data (5, 6) to identify
12 differentially expressed gene products in glioblastoma by performing whole transcriptome gene expression
13 profiling. We found that the gene encoding the cell division cycle associated 2, CDCA2, was among those
14 whose expression was most different in human glioblastoma tumors when comparing total transcription
15 between tumor and normal brain tissue. CDCA2 expression levels were significantly increased in
16 glioblastoma tumors as compared to the non-transformed brain. CDCA2 function at the systems level was
17 assessed by studying whole transcriptome transcriptional co-regulation in the transformed brain. CDCA2
18 is a target of interest for the treatment of glioblastoma, as part of a rationally designed chemotherapeutic
19 regimen that utilizes gene expression data from patient tumors and healthy non-transformed tissues to
20 maximize efficacy and safety and minimize toxicity.

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26 Keywords: CDCA2, cell division cycle associated 2, glioblastoma, systems biology of glioblastoma,
27 targeted therapeutics in glioblastoma.

1 Brain cancer encompasses a spectrum of solid tumors that affect the brain in children and adults
2 including medulloblastoma, neuroblastoma, and glioblastoma (7). Rational development of targeted
3 therapeutics to treat patients with glioblastoma can be supported by an enhanced understanding of
4 fundamental transcriptional differences that define the glioblastoma tumor. To discover genes associated
5 with glioblastoma in humans in an unbiased fashion and at the systems level, we compared total
6 transcription in the normal brain and in the glioblastoma tumor using published and public human
7 glioblastoma microarray and RNA-sequencing data (5, 6) to identify a molecular signature or fingerprint
8 of glioblastoma, among the most lethal and difficult to treat solid tumors affecting adults. We describe
9 here identification of a potential therapeutic target in glioblastoma based on quantitative whole
10 transcriptome methods.

11 **Methods**

12 We utilized microarray datasets GSE116520 (5) and GSE184643 (6) for this differential gene
13 expression analysis of the brain cancer glioblastoma in humans using R-based computational methods
14 (GEO2R). GSE116520 was generated using Illumina HumanHT-12 V4.0 expression beadchip
15 technology; for this analysis, we used $n=8$ control brain tissue and $n=17$ glioblastoma tumors, and the
16 analysis was performed using platform GPL10558. GSE184643 was generated using Illumina NovaSeq
17 6000 (Homo sapiens) technology; for this analysis, we used $n=3$ control brain tissue and $n=3$ glioblastoma
18 tumors, and the analysis was performed using platform GPL24676. The Benjamini and Hochberg method
19 of p-value adjustment was used for ranking of differential expression but raw p-values were used to assess
20 statistical significance of global differential expression. Log-transformation of data was auto-detected, and
21 the NCBI generated category of platform annotation was used. SEEK was utilized for transcriptional
22 co-regulation studies (8).

23 **Results**

24 We harnessed the power of whole transcriptome technologies and cross-laboratory validation (5, 6)
25 to discover in an unbiased fashion and at the transcriptome level the most distinguishing gene expression
26 features of the human brain cancer glioblastoma.

27 CDCA2 is differentially expressed in glioblastoma.

28 1. Primary tumors of the brain from humans with glioblastoma

$n=8$ normal brain tissues (human)

$n=17$ primary tumors (brain; human; glioblastoma)

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
ILMN_1660654	5.07E-05	-4.5206901	1.503199	-0.79264884	CDCA2	6091/47229	87.1

29 Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in normal brain tissues and glioblastoma
30 tumor tissue, we discovered differential expression of cell division cycle associated 2, encoded by CDCA2
31 in glioblastoma in humans (**Chart 1**). The expression of CDCA2 changed more than 85% of the human
32 brain and brain tumor transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in
33 this case, 47,229 transcripts (“Rank”). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of
34 CDCA2 messenger RNA in glioblastoma tumors, demonstrating up-regulation of CDCA2 during
35 transformation of the brain from normal brain tissue to glioblastoma.

2. Primary tumors of the brain from humans with brain cancer: glioblastoma.

$n=3$ normal brain tissues (human)

$n=3$ primary tumors (brain; human; glioblastoma)

ID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
157313	1.35E-06	1.034	-4.8319808	-4.99568652	62.1	CDCA2	896/19678	95.4

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in normal brain tissues and glioblastoma tumors in a second RNA-sequencing dataset from independent investigators and a separate patient cohort, we validated differential expression of cell division cycle associated 2, encoded by CDCA2 in glioblastoma in humans (**Chart 2**). The expression of CDCA2 here changed more than 95% of the human brain and brain tumor transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 19,678 transcripts (“Rank”). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of CDCA2 messenger RNA in glioblastoma tumors, demonstrating up-regulation of CDCA2 during transformation of the brain from normal brain tissue to glioblastoma.

Thus, CDCA2 is a gene whose differential expression defines the transcriptional landscape of the glioblastoma subtype in humans.

CDCA2 transcriptional co-regulation.

Finally, we utilized a separate systems methodology that utilizes whole transcriptome data to provide insight into molecular function of a gene product by evaluating the transcriptional network within which it operates through identification of co-regulated gene partners.

In the transformed brain, CDCA2 was transcriptionally co-regulated with BIRC5, KIF20A, KIF23, ASPM, AURKA, ESCO2, TPX2, MKI67, PBK, TTK, and HJURP.

Thus, blind comparative transcriptome analysis of glioblastomas revealed differential expression of CDCA2 as among the most significant transcriptional features of glioblastoma tumors; systems level query into CDCA2 molecular function across multiple tissues at the transcriptome level revealed its co-regulation with BIRC5, KIF20A, KIF23, ASPM, AURKA, ESCO2, TPX2, MKI67, PBK, TTK, and HJURP.

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Discussion

We found by mining published and public microarray and RNA-sequencing data (5, 6) that the cell division cycle associated 2, CDCA2, was among the genes most differentially expressed in the primary tumors of patients with glioblastoma; CDCA2 was expressed at significantly higher levels in glioblastoma tumors as compared to the brain. CDCA2 is a target of interest for rationally designed medical treatment of glioblastoma, a difficult to treat adult solid tumor.

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